

A META-ANALYSIS ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CONTEXT-BASED APPROACH IN IMPROVING THE SECONDARY STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN SCIENCE

James C. Ollero, Maricar S. Prudente

Department of Science Education, Br. Andrew Gonzalez FSC College of Education, De La Salle University, Manila City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15475648>

ABSTRACT

Science education is increasingly emphasized in developing countries due to its role in enhancing citizens' scientific knowledge and competencies. However, students often struggle with science curricula that are dense in content, terminology, and abstract concepts, resulting in uneven academic performance. A context-based approach to science teaching has emerged as a promising solution, enabling curriculum and instruction to be grounded in real-world contexts. Despite its growing popularity and reported success, there remains a need to consolidate and assess existing research to determine the approach's effectiveness across different secondary grade levels and scientific disciplines. This study employed a meta-analytic method to evaluate the impact of the context-based approach on secondary students' academic achievement in science. Fourteen empirical studies published between 2011 and 2024 from Africa, Asia, and Europe met the inclusion criteria. Of these, six studies ($n = 572$) focused on Senior High School (SHS) students, while eight ($n = 747$) examined Junior High School (JHS) students. Research articles were retrieved through platforms like Crossref, Google Scholar, OpenAlex, and Semantic Scholar, with Harzing's Publish or Perish ensuring comprehensive coverage. Data including sample sizes, means, and standard deviations were analyzed using JAMOVI to calculate Hedge's g and generate forest and funnel plots, along with the Begg-Mazumdar test. Moderator analysis was conducted via Comprehensive Meta-Analysis version 4. Results showed a strong positive effect of the context-based approach on students' science achievement ($ES = 2.14$), with no significant variation across grade levels or scientific domains. Future research is encouraged to explore the nuanced factors influencing its implementation and

effectiveness.

Keywords: *Academic Achievement, Effect Size, Context-Based Learning, Meta-Analysis, Science Instruction, Systematic Review*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the 21st century education, it is undeniable that globally, science education is becoming more and more important in developing countries as it increases citizens' scientific knowledge and skills. In the Philippine context, Republic Act No. 10533 or popularly known as the Enhanced Education Act of 2013, established mandatory science education in the Philippines with the main objective of producing individuals with a scientific background who can make major contributions to the community's growth. Science courses are filled with a plethora of technical terminology, jargons, and concepts that are vitally important to comprehend and clarify the connections between different organizations, processes, and topics. This is also posited in the study conducted by Samikwo (2013), as cited by Wai & Khine (2020), that the main difficulties encountered in studying biology and other science subjects were the terminology employed in the subject matter, misspellings of scientific phrases, and the stringent nature of biology assessments. Therefore, effective instruction in every classroom is necessary to increase biology learning for all students. Presentation and explanation must be clear in order for instruction to be effective. The scientific investigations of Smith and Meux (1962), quoted in Westwood (1996), suggests that teachers' imprecise explanations are the main cause of students' misunderstanding. Ineffective explanations frequently cause confusion in learners, which impedes their ability to learn. In addition, students are unable to finish the study due to a lack of teaching and learning methodologies (Hasruddin & Putri, 2014). Furthermore, according to Osborne and Collins (2001), cited by Etorbro & Fabinu (2017), the overabundance of content in the curriculum is causing students' interest in science to decline. Moreover, it usually has nothing to do with the facts of life. It is also necessary to have more discussions on subjects of interest, the lack of venues for artistic expression, the separation of science and society, and the significance of particular scientific fields. For this reason, students may often be discombobulated and can often cause learning fatigue to students in biology. Thus, Köse & Tosun (2015) stated that the nature of learning must be taken into account in order to enhance both the teaching-learning process and the learning results. One significant approach to addressing these issues has been to base curriculum design and classroom instruction on "context." In order for this to be successful, the educational framework that best represents the concept of "context" needs to be designed in a way that effectively addresses the related curricular and social issues (Gilbert, 2006). "Coherence," "connection," and/or "relationship" are expressed by the term in its related noun "contextus." Something new placed inside a larger perspective needs a context to give it a logical structural significance and meaning (Gilbert, 2006).

Many countries, including the United States, Germany, Israel, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom, have adopted the context-based approach (Pilot and Bulte, 2006;

Gilbert, 2006; Bennett and Holman, 2003). It is evident that context-based approaches are becoming more popular across all age groups, from elementary school to tertiary education. Context-based learning strives to generate scientifically-literate adult citizens while also promoting motivation, assimilation of science subjects, and acquisition of concepts related to science (Bennett and Holman, 2003). Interestingly, Dioneda (2019) argued that the K–12 curriculum in the Philippines emphasizes localization and contextualization as novel approaches to the process of teaching and learning.

One beneficial and important tool that aids students acquire things meaningfully and form favorable attitudes about them is learning in context (Bennett et al., 2007). As such, in connection to this, several studies have shown links between the usage of context-based approach and the improvement of the students' academic achievement in science. Moreover, studies on the effectiveness of context-based learning were compared to the usage of conventional approaches employed in the educative process of science education. Many studies have examined the impact of the context-based approach on students' attitudes and comprehension of scientific concepts, taking into account its many benefits. Bennett et al. (2003) conducted systematic reviews on the benefits of a context-based approach, with a focus on the affective domain. Ramsden (1997) contrasted how well students performed while teaching chemistry using a context-based method to a traditional technique. The study indicates that while there is no disparity in comprehension levels, there seem to be some advantages to using a context-based strategy in terms of stirring students' interest in science. Additionally, the investigation of Gutwill-Wise (2001) was done as he was working with college students who had taken beginning chemistry courses. He conducted a comparison between matched groups of students who had taken a traditional approach to chemistry and those who had taken the context-based approach. According to the study, students who used the context-based approach in both universities gained a deeper comprehension of chemistry than their counterparts who used the traditional technique. Additionally, Çiğdemoğlu (2012) discovered that a context-based strategy is extremely successful in raising literacy, achievement, and comprehension among learners. Moreover, it stimulates the intrinsic motivation of students to understand and learn chemistry.

Even though the context-based approach to science education is becoming more and more popular for raising students' academic achievement, there is still an increasing demand for synthesis and assessment investigations to determine its usefulness across different secondary grade levels and scientific disciplines. When a group of studies are sufficiently similar with regard to individuals, interventions, and outcomes to provide a valuable summary, meta-analysis should be used (Haidich, 2010). In order to evaluate, examine, and investigate the efficacy of the context-based approach, particularly with regard to secondary students' academic accomplishment in science, the researcher used meta-analysis. To the greatest extent of the researcher's knowledge, for the past 14 years, there has been an urge for a meta-analysis of context-based approaches with a focus on secondary students' academic achievement. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the various context-based approaches implemented in science classrooms and offer an assessment and evaluation of empirical studies. This study will also evaluate other relevant information on the academic achievements of secondary

students using context-based approach.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of Context-Based Approach in improving the secondary students' academic achievement in various scientific disciplines. Specifically, it aims to answer:

1. How effective are context-based approaches in improving students' academic achievement?
2. Is there a significant difference on the effect sizes of junior high school and senior high school in relation to their academic achievement using Context-Based Approach in science?
3. Is there a significant difference on the effect sizes of different scientific fields using Context-Based Approach in science in relation to the secondary students' academic achievement?
4. What were the context-based instructional strategies that were investigated and employed to improve students' academic achievement?

METHODOLOGY

In order to ascertain the variations among the variables, which include the students' grade levels and the various disciplines of science, the researcher employed the meta-analysis to investigate and determine the effectiveness of the Context-Based Approach on improving the academic achievement of secondary students. A meta-analysis concentrates on the integration of results from several studies that made it easier to analyze and assess different empirical studies on the academic performance of high school science students using a context-based approach in a transparent and logical manner (Gough et al., 2017). Meta-analysis is an increasingly common instrument utilized for evaluating the effect of an intervention in a variety of experimental studies. In addition to providing a projection of the average treatment impact and its variation across studies, the meta-analysis will open up novel opportunities for future research aiming to draw general inferences about the status quo of the literature (Pigott & Polanin, 2017; Creswell, 2013).

Literature Search Procedure

The researcher established the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this meta-analysis before scanning peer-reviewed journal articles. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) procedure served as guidance and direction in the selection of pertinent and noteworthy research, as shown in Figure 1 (Antonio, 2022). In general, the researcher has searched databases of journal research publications and examined academic citations using the software tool Harzing's Publish or Perish. For retrieving research articles from Crossref, Google Scholar, OpenAlex, and

Semantic Scholar, the researcher used Publish or Perish. On purpose, the search was restricted to the period from 2011 up to the first quarter of 2024. Additionally, the researcher has included descriptors like "contextual teaching and learning," "context-based approach," "science," "achievement," "science education," "effectiveness," and "secondary students" to meta-search engines. Until all relevant research and journal articles were found, these terms or descriptors were sporadically and indiscriminately entered into the meta-search engine with the term "context-based approach" or "context-based learning/teaching" used consistently.

Figure 1. Literature Search Using PRISMA 2020 flow diagram

The pipeline diagram for the PRISMA-based protocol literature search is shown in Figure 1. Several meta-search engines returned a total of 2,194 research publications during the first literature search, which was specifically limited to the period from January 2011 to March 2024. Twenty-seven (27) duplicates were eliminated by using a data cleansing tool or an online duplicate checker. However, due to formatting inaccuracies such as variations in word choice or syntax and quantitative presentations, some duplicates (n=45) were missed by the web-based software and required to be manually validated and eliminated. After the abstracts of the papers were carefully and rigorously screened, 86 articles from the remaining pool were evaluated based on the predetermined criteria for inclusion and exclusion.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Only those studies that satisfied the criteria of this study were carefully vetted and scrutinized. To systematically select the empirical studies, the researcher created inclusion criteria that comprised the following components:

- a) online accessibility of the research article's full-text copy;
- b) the manuscript must be authored in English or translated into it;
- c) the research paper ought to be categorized as an empirical investigation;
- d) published within and between the period of January 2011 to March 2024;
- e) the study's title or abstract ought to make it apparent that a context-based approach is included.
- f) utilization of experimental or quasi-experimental research methodologies;
- g) adequacy of quantitative/statistical data (e.g., posttest means, standard deviation)
- h) indication of academic achievement as one of the principal findings;
- i) conduct of research in a secondary level (junior and senior high school), and;
- j) concentrate on any discipline of science.

The following criteria led to the exclusion of 72 journal articles from the preliminary pool of 86 studies, including: a) full-text copy not available online: 9; b) did not employ experimental and/or quasi-experimental methods: 14; c) was not a previously published study (e.g., thesis, dissertation): 2; d) did not concentrate on academic achievement: 8; e) inadequate quantitative data: 32; f) published in conference proceeding: 7. After the 86 research articles pointed out earlier were eliminated or excluded, fourteen (14) research articles were found to be suitable for the meta-analysis. An asterisk (*) has been placed next to each of the fourteen (14) research articles in the list of references.

Effect Size Calculation

The effect size is frequently employed to ascertain the standardized mean differences. Standard Mean Differences (SMDs) are often evaluated using Cohen's d or Hedges' g. Small sample sizes substantially skew the results, however the pooled standard deviation is used to divide the difference between sample means of a continuous response by

Cohen's d. Hedges' g adjusts for this bias through the application of a correction factor (Lin & Aloe, 2021). Glen (2016) found that Hedges' g is more accurate and reliable than Cohen's d, especially when small sample sizes (<20) are considered. Therefore, in order to determine the effectiveness of context-based strategies in enhancing secondary students' academic achievement, the researcher utilized the JAMOVI program that was created by Jonathon Love, Damian Dropmann, and Ravi Selker developed in 2017 to determine and calculate the effect sizes, commonly referred to as Hedges' g, for 14 research publications. Furthermore, the moderator analysis of this meta-analysis was calculated and carried out using Biostat, Inc.'s Comprehensive Meta-Analysis (CMA) version 4. This software was employed to carry out the moderator analysis, which categorized and compared the data, while the JAMOVI program was utilized for identifying other relevant statistics, such as heterogeneity, fixed and randomized effect sizes, and forest plots. In addition, Harbord et al. (2009) suggested that it requires at least ten (10) empirical studies that may be subjected to the funnel plot symmetry test. In order to illustrate publication bias in the collection of empirical studies, the researcher used the previously indicated software to create a funnel plot in response to this recommendation. For the purpose of ascertaining any disparities in the efficacy of context-based techniques across categories such student grade level, academic achievement, and scientific discipline studied, mixed effects analysis was also employed. The Begg-Mazumdar test was applied to calculate and quantify publication bias. A 95% confidence level was included with every test, and p-values less than 0.05 were regarded as statistically significant.

RESULTS

This meta-analysis includes 1,319 secondary students (junior and senior high school) from 14 qualified empirical studies. The frequency of studies, student grade levels, and various scientific subjects are presented and depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. Frequency of students' grade level and the scientific discipline studied

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Junior High School (JHS)	8	57.14%
Senior High School (SHS)	6	42.86%
Scientific Discipline		
Biology	4	28.57%
Science and Technology	4	28.57%
Physics	3	21.43%
Chemistry	3	21.43%
TOTAL	14	100%

Table 1 illustrates that eight (8) of the research obtained between 2011 and 2024 employed junior high school (JHS) students (n = 747), while the remaining six (6) empirical studies used senior high school students (n = 572) as study participants. Sadi-

Yilmaz et al. (2022) posited that students find it more difficult to understand science when topics and concepts are presented in summation design in science classrooms, which abstracts the subject matter. Instead, students will comprehend science courses more fully if they can connect and relate the subject to real-world scenarios. The study's impact on student assessments increased in lockstep with the importance of education expanding as a result of scientific and technological breakthroughs. The two prominent instances of concurrently implemented international student assessment programs are PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) and TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study). One of the main features of context-based science education is that it presents scientific concepts to students in contexts that show how they apply to actual circumstances (İlhan et al., 2016; Schwartz, 2006; Sadi-Yılmaz, 2013). According to Bülbül et al. (2019), it is imperative that the contexts developed or selected for context-based teachers (CBT) meet certain criteria and are of a quality that will captivate students' interest. Table 1 shows the context-based approach's distributed implementation in science fields such as physics, chemistry, biology, and science and technology in secondary education. This suggests that the context-based approach is a prevalent teaching strategy for a variety of scientific disciplines. The total effect size (ES) of the gathered and chosen journal articles is highlighted in Table 2, along with other relevant data such as the number of studies (k), variance, standard error (SE), confidence intervals (CI), and Z-value. On the other hand, Table 3 depicts the heterogeneity or the variability of the research that were gathered.

Table 2. Overall Effect Size

Random-Effects Model (k = 14)

	Estimate	se	Z	p	CI Lower Bound	CI Upper Bound
Intercept	2.14	0.511	4.19	<.001	1.142	3.145

Note. Tau² Estimator: Hedges

Table 3. Heterogeneity Statistics

Tau	Tau ²	I ²	H ²	R ²	df	Q	p
1.878	3.5274 (SE=1.4409)	98.32%	59.533	.	13.000	195.431	<.001

The calculated Q statistic (Q > df), which is illustrated and confirmed in Table 3, indicates high heterogeneity, indicating that the empirical studies included for this meta-analysis do not have identical or shared effect sizes. Nevertheless, since the derived p value (p<.001) is under the p value of .05 and the significant level is at the p >.05 level, it is not significant.

This result indicates that the random-effect technique is the most suitable strategy to synthesize the studies in this meta-analysis due to the fact that it suggests the pattern of distribution of effect sizes is exceptionally diverse or heterogeneous in nature (Borenstein et al., 2009). Moreover, as indicated in Table 2's overall weighted random effect size of 2.14, the implementation of a context-based approach has a remarkably positive and large effect on the academic achievement of secondary students. Borenstein et al. (2009) further stated that I² achieved a high score of 98.32, emphasizing the need for moderator or subgroup analysis. The forest plot and a thorough analysis of each meta-analyzed study are presented in Figure 2, which additionally provides context for the findings and demonstrates the variety of impact sizes.

Figure 2. Forest plot of the meta-analysis results of the 14 included empirical studies

The experimental group, which used a context-based approach, outperformed the control group, which used the conventional approach, in the general distribution of effect sizes, as shown by the forest plot. The lower confidence interval denotes how essential the studies conducted by Lubis & Rahmania (2022), Agyei (2022), Kazeni & Onwu (2013), and Ahmad (2017) were to this meta-analysis. The context-based approach, which has been scientifically proven in research to have substantial benefits for the experimental group, was validated using Fail-Safe N analysis. The salient findings of the publication bias assessment are shown in Tables 4 and 5.

Table 4. Publication Bias Assessment

Test Name	Value	p
Fail-Safe N	3079.000	< .001
Begg and Mazumdar Rank Correlation	0.516	0.010
Egger's Regression	6.476	< .001
Trim and Fill Number of Studies	0.000	.

Note. Fail-safe N Calculation Using the Rosenthal Approach

Table 4 confirms that, pursuant to the Fail-Safe N analysis, the meta-analysis of 14 empirical studies is highly valid ($p < .001$) and resistant to publication bias. Nevertheless, this conclusion was not further reinforced by the funnel plot and Begg-Mazumdar test, which are shown in Figure 3 and Table 4, respectively.

Table 5. Classic Fail-safe N

The Resistance of the Meta-Analysis versus Publication Bias	
Z-value	24.57919
p-value	0.00000
Alpha value	0.05000
Alpha value for the Z-value	1.95996
N	14
Number of missing studies that would bring p-value to > alpha	2188

The findings of Table 4—which indicate that the meta-analysis of 14 empirical studies is highly valid ($p < .001$) and resistant to publication bias—are supported by Table 5's results from the Classic Fail-Safe N analysis. Based on the results, 2,188 additional empirical studies are required to refute, invalidate, or disprove the meta-analysis' findings. This conclusion was not further supported by the funnel plot and Begg-Mazumdar test, which are shown in Figure 3 and Table 4, respectively.

Figure 3. Funnel Plot of Standard Error by Standardized Mean Difference

As evident in Figure 3, the funnel plot indicated that, when compared to the 95% confidence level, nearly all of the studies—that is, 10 out of the 14 empirical studies included in this meta-analysis—are outliers, which contribute to the asymmetry of the results. This outcome, which has a p-value of .010 ($p < .05$) in the Begg-Mazumdar test results incorporated into the publication bias assessment displayed in Table 4, further supports the existence of publication bias among the studies. Analyses for funnel plot asymmetry and funnel plots itself are frequently employed for seeking at bias in meta-analysis findings. There are also other reasonable and scientific justifications and explanations for funnel plot asymmetry, therefore it should not be confused with publication bias (Sterne et al., 2011). Moreover, Zwetsloot et al. (2017) contended that the existence and degree of publication bias are overestimated in funnel plots of the Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) presented alongside the standard error (SE) due to their susceptibility to distortion. Primary studies with small sample sizes and an intervention effect showed higher distortion. To support, a moderator analysis was used to determine the significant difference in effect sizes between the grade levels of the students and scientific disciplines, and the results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Moderator Analysis of secondary students' grade level and scientific disciplined studied

Moderator Random Effects Model	k	ES	SE	Variance	95% CI		Z	p	Heterogeneity*		
					Lower	Upper			Q	df (Q)	p
Level of Education	14	2.008	0.280	0.078	1.460	2.556	7.179	0.000	1.035	1	0.309
JHS	8	2.257	0.367	0.135	1.537	2.977	6.143	0.000			
SHS	6	1.694	0.414	0.171	0.882	2.505	4.091	0.000			
Scientific Discipline	14	2.028	0.364	0.133	1.315	2.742	5.570	0.000	2.843	3	0.416
Biology	4	1.723	0.522	0.272	0.701	2.745	3.303	0.001			
Chemistry	3	1.402	0.596	0.356	0.233	2.571	2.350	0.019			
Physics	3	2.619	0.625	0.391	1.393	3.844	4.188	0.000			
Science and Technology	4	2.425	0.558	0.311	1.331	3.519	4.346	0.000			

The moderator analysis used to find the significant difference in impact sizes between the academic achievement of secondary students' grade-level and scientific disciplines when a context-based approach was used in science instruction is displayed in Table 6. While using a context-based approach has a positive and considerably large effect size on improving secondary students' academic achievement, JHS and SHS had large and positive impact sizes of 2.257 and 1.694, correspondingly, based on education level. It is apparent, therefore, that the context-based strategy used in JHS had a comparatively larger effect size than it did in SHS. Further, there is no significant difference, as indicated by the heterogeneity results ($Q > df$; $p > .05$), suggesting that the JHS and SHS have similar effect sizes. Furthermore, Biology, Chemistry, Physics, and Science and Technology obtained significant and positive effect sizes of 1.723, 1.402, 2.619, and 2.425, respectively, in terms of the scientific fields to which context-based approach was applied. It is noteworthy that, with impact sizes of 2.619 and 2.425, respectively, Physics and Science and Technology have earned the biggest values among these scientific subjects. The many scientific disciplines appear to have a significant and positive effect size, as indicated by the total effect size of 2.028. The absence of statistically significant impacts in the heterogeneity of scientific disciplines ($Q < df$; $p > .05$) suggests that the context-based approach, when applied to different scientific fields, may have similar effect sizes. The review's conclusions imply that, as compared to conventional approaches, the impact of a context-based approach on the academic achievement of students is constant across every grade level and disciplines of science. Even if the effect sizes across various disciplines of science were similar, the researcher investigated the various instructional strategies which utilized a context-based approach. The several context-based strategies used in the 14 empirical studies included in this meta-analysis are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Context-Based Instructional Strategies utilized by the obtained studies

Context-Based Strategies	Frequency	Percentage
Contextual Learning	14	100%
Authentic Assessment	14	100%
Problem-Based Learning	6	42.86%
Place-Based Learning	4	28.57%
Interdisciplinary Learning	3	21.43%
Simulations and Role Playing	3	21.43%
Cultural and Global Perspectives	3	21.43%

Table 7 indicated that using authentic assessment and learning from contextual learning are the most widely employed and implemented context-based approaches. However, in contrast, the approaches that are most rarely employed are those related to interdisciplinary learning, role-playing and simulations, and cultural and global perspectives. ICT, technology-based instructional instruments, and the assessment and evaluation of students' understanding about the scientific concepts or topics as products of students' context-based activities were also integrated during instruction in the process of analyzing the methodology and approach of the studies collected and included in this meta-analysis.

DISCUSSION

Context-based learning has garnered a lot of interest in science education because it has the potential to enhance students' comprehension and utilization of scientific ideas in real-world settings (Baran and Sozbilir, 2018). The usefulness of context-based learning strategies has been examined in several studies for enhancing learning outcomes and student engagement (Gebre et al., 2014; Patterson et al., 2011; Sevia et al., 2018; Valdman et al., 2016; van Dulmen et al., 2022; Vogelzang et al., 2019). According to research by Akcay (2009), including real-world situations in science lessons increases students' enthusiasm, interest, and understanding.

Similar to this, a study by Yu et al. (2015) demonstrated that context-based learning experiences raise students' conceptual comprehension and problem-solving abilities in science. Learning in context, the incorporation of actual experiences and real-life scenarios is widely recognized as a promising approach to teaching science, since it can enhance students' understanding as well as application of the principles of science (Nagarajan & Overton, 2019). Evidently, a number of research demonstrated that applying a context-based approach may aid students do better academically. However, in the last few decades, there has been a pressing need to review and evaluate data in terms of its applicability and efficacy. Thus, in order to assess how well context-based scientific education improves the academic achievement of secondary students, the researcher used meta-analysis.

The findings of this research proved that junior and senior high school students, as well as those learning an array of scientific disciplines, frequently use the context-based approach. An overall effect size of 2.14, indicating a positive and large effect, was found in the meta-analysis of 14 empirical studies involving 1,319 secondary students (JHS and SHS) that were published between 2011 and 2024. It has been determined that the acquisition of the conceptual understanding of learners is a variable result of context-based instruction, which demonstrates that the application of a context-based approach primarily proves effective. Students who participated in context-based learning showed a higher level of conceptual comprehension than those getting conventional instruction (Agyei, 2022).

Specifically, in analyzing each empirical study involved, majority of the studies included in this meta-analysis procured large effect sizes. These studies include the study of Bello et al. (2023), Dioneda (2019), Ozkan and Selcuk (2015), Azhar et al. (2021), Jusriana et al. (2022), Ahmad (2017), Agyei (2022) Dumanjog (2020), Asrizal et al. (2019), Magwilang (2016), Kazeni and Onwu (2013) and Lubis and Rahmania (2022). This is due to the fact that they have obtained effect sizes of 7.75, 3.64, 3.63, 2.92, 2.64, 1.87, 1.68, 1.61, 1.32, 1.20, 1.18 and 1.14, respectively. On the one hand, the study of Taratara-Fadero (2022) obtained medium effect size of 0.60. While the study of Bacay and Herrera (2020) procured no effect size (ES = 0.00). The overall effect size (ES = 2.14) is positive and large, demonstrating the effectiveness of context-based science learning and teaching in addition to raising the academic achievement of secondary students. The results of the meta-analysis show that a context-based strategy is more effective than a traditional science instruction approach, favoring the experiment side ($p < .001$). Because there were few selected empirical studies and varying effect sizes across grade levels and various fields of science, the researcher conducted an analysis of publication bias. The researchers employed the Begg-Mazumdar test to explore further the possibility of publication bias after noticing asymmetry on the funnel plot related to the outliers. A p -value of .010 ($p > .05$) from the Begg-Mazumdar test indicated publication bias in the meta-analysis. However, additional research could bolster the claim that using a context-based approach rather than the conventional approach for science instruction in high school is generally more successful.

The unusually high I^2 value ($I^2 = 98.32$) necessitates the execution of a subgroup or moderator analysis (Borenstein et al., 2009). Moderator analysis was used to examine how well a context-based approach worked for students in various scientific disciplines and at different grade levels. JHS and SHS's context-based approaches showed large, positive effect sizes of 2.257 and 1.694, respectively. The JHS and SHS produced a large and favorable effect of 2.008 when they combined their effect sizes. A detailed analysis of the data indicates that JHS outperformed SHS in terms of effect magnitude. According to Yilmaz et al. (2022), research suggests that learners at different levels have diverse outcomes from CBT. Learners with lower cognitive levels respond more positively to context-based learning, as noted by Suryawati and Osman (2017). This is supported by the observation that young learners are more explorers and inquisitive than adult learners, and that curiosity appears to help with learning (Liquin & Gopnik, 2022). Additionally, it is reasonable to presume that JHS students' cognitive skills are lower than SHS students'.

There have not been many specific contrasts of exploration throughout development. In general, adult learners will outperform young learners on cognitive activities, particularly those that involve investigation, given their many cognitive advantages over younger learners. Conversely, there are circumstances in which we can witness a contrary, illogical developmental pattern—young learners might explore more than adult learners. In particular, there is evidence to show that adults and children may come to different findings about how to reconcile these interests. In real-world learning difficulties, there is frequently an agreement between exploration and exploitation. However, given the data, it appears that JHS and SHS would have comparable impact sizes because there was no significant value for heterogeneity. This result indicates that using a context-based approach benefits JHS and SHS pupils equally. However, applying it necessitates ongoing observation. When teaching science utilizing a context-based approach, it is highly recommended that teachers be present at all times, serving as an advisor, facilitator, and supervisor. Future studies should look into how well teachers are able to implement context-based instruction in their specific science classes.

The context-based approach produced significant and positive effect sizes of 1.723, 1.402, 2.619, and 2.425, respectively, when applied to a variety of scientific subjects, including biology, chemistry, physics, and science and technology. When the collected data from several scientific disciplines were combined, an overall effect size of 2.028 was calculated, suggesting that the context-based approach has a significant impact on students' academic achievement across a range of scientific disciplines. Additionally, the heterogeneity finding of .416 ($p > .05$) shows that academic achievement of secondary students is not influenced by the context-based approach implemented in different scientific disciplines when compared to traditional teaching approach. These results showed that, in many fields of science, utilizing a context-based approach is generally more beneficial for secondary students when compared to the traditional approach. Meanwhile, it was found that neither the discipline of science in which it was applied nor the grade level of students had any impact on the context-based approach. Thus, it is recommended that additional study be conducted on the factors affecting students' academic achievement as a consequence of using context-based approaches.

The researcher examined and evaluated the diverse strategies employed by the empirical studies in using the context-based approaches. The majority of the combined studies used contextual learning (100%), authentic assessment (100%), and problem-based learning (42.86%). These concepts were the cornerstones of implementing a context-based approach in science instruction. Since it stresses the integration of real-world situations and authentic experiences to enhance students' understanding and implementation of scientific principles, context-based learning is widely acknowledged as an effective way to teaching science (Nagarajan & Overton, 2019). Lemke (2001), who emphasized the need of situating learning in relevant situations, conducted one of the landmark studies on the subject. Lemke's sociocultural theory (2001) states that social interactions and the use of real-world tasks are crucial for assisting students' cognitive development and understanding of scientific concepts. Numerous studies have examined the impact of context-based learning on students' motivation and engagement in science classrooms. For instance, Fortus et al. (2005) found that integrating real-world scenarios

and problem-solving exercises increased students' excitement and interest in science in a research involving high school students. Therefore, it is recommended that future research evaluating scientific students' academic achievement focus on learning through problem-based learning, contextual learning, and authentic evaluation. To take full advantage of the efficacy of the context-based approach, it is advised that a variety of approaches be integrated into it, and that learning outcomes be assessed taking into account a wide range of factors other than secondary students' academic performance. Future studies may also look into the effects of a context-based approach on students' affective domains, such as their character development and socio-emotional aspect.

Conclusions

The findings of this meta-analysis reveal that the context-based approach to science instruction has a strong and positive impact on secondary students' academic achievement, with an effect size of 2.14. Notably, this positive impact remains consistent regardless of the students' grade levels (JHS or SHS) or the specific science disciplines involved. This suggests that embedding science content within meaningful, real-life contexts can effectively enhance students' understanding and performance in science across various educational settings.

Recommendations

In light of these results, future studies are encouraged to go beyond general academic performance and delve into how context-based teaching affects different cognitive, emotional, and subject-specific learning outcomes. Additionally, comparative research examining the implementation of context-based approaches across countries, cultural settings, and school systems would be valuable. Further investigation into the conditions, strategies, and barriers that influence successful integration of context-based teaching in science classrooms is also recommended to guide both policy and practice.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Acknowledgments

The primary author would like to express his profound gratitude towards the Department of Science and Technology - Science Education Institute (DOST-SEI) for the scholarship granted through the Capacity Building Program for Science and Mathematics Education (CBPSME) that made the completion of this paper possible. The authors also extend their sincere thanks to the anonymous reviewers and editors for their valuable feedback and support in improving this manuscript.

REFERENCES

- *Agyei, C.A. (2022) Effect of Context-Based and Conventional Teaching Approaches on Students' Achievement in Genetics. *British Journal of Education*, 10 (11), pp.121-139
- *Ahmad, S. S. (2017). The Impact of Context-based Instructional Approach on Students Academic Achievement and Retention of Hydrocarbon Concepts among Science Secondary Students in Kano State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Sciences & Environmental Sustainability*, 3, 44–58.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/361228654>
- Akcay, B. (2009). Problem-based learning in science education. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 6(1), 28-38.
- Antonio, R. P. (2022). Effectiveness of Blended Instructional Approach in Improving Students' Scientific Learning Outcomes: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Higher Education Theory & Practice*, 22(5).
- *Asrizal, N., Amran, A., Ananda, A., & Festiyed, N. (2019). Effects of science student worksheet of motion in daily life theme in adaptive contextual teaching model on academic achievement of students. *Journal of Physics. Conference Series*, 1185, 012093. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1185/1/012093>
- *Azhar, Z., Suparno, N., Rukun, K., Jama, J., Effendi, H., & Muskhir, M. (2021). Effectiveness of E-Learning Approach to Contextual Teaching and Learning in Improving Students 'Ability. *Journal of Physics. Conference Series*, 1783(1), 012110. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1783/1/012110>
- *Bacay, M.M. & Herrera, A.S. (2020). Context-Based Learning in Teaching Senior High School: Basis for Science Instructional Material Development. (2020). In *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences* (Vol. 7, Issue 1, pp. 73–81). <https://www.apjeas.apjmr.com>
- Baran, M., & Sozbilir, M. (2018). An application of context-and problem-based learning (C-PBL) into teaching thermodynamics. *Research in Science Education*, 48, 663-689. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-016-9583-1>
- *Bello, J. B., Concon, L. S., Polache, M. C. C., Ayaton, M. J. C., Manlicayan, R. D., Campomanes, J. P., & Saro, J. M. (2023). Contextualized and Localized Science Teaching and Learning Materials and Its Characteristics to Improve Students' Learning Performance. Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7607686>
- Bennett, J., Campbell, B., Hogarth, S., & Lubben, F. (2007). A systematic review of the effects on high school students of context-based and science-technology (STS) approaches to the teaching of science. York, UK: Department of Educational Studies The University of York. Retrieved June, 12, 2007.
- Bennett, J. & Holman, J., (2003). Context-based approaches to the teaching of chemistry: what are they and what are their effects? Gilbert, J.K., Jong De O., Justi, R., Treagust, D., F., Van Driel, J., H., (Eds) *Chemical Education: Towards Research-Based Practice*, (165-185) Kluwer Academic Publishers, New York, Boston, Dordrecht, London, Moscow.
- Borenstein, M., Cooper, H., Hedges, L., & Valentine, J. (2009). Effect sizes for continuous data. *The handbook of research synthesis and meta-analysis*, 2, 221-

- Bülbül, M. Ş., Elmas, R., & Eryılmaz, A. (2019). Determining the appealing contexts for physics and chemistry regarding the context discipline relationship. *Mehmet Akif Ersoy Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 50, 451-479.
<https://doi.org/10.21764/maeuefd.364766>
- Çiğdemoğlu, C. (2012). Effectiveness of Context-Based Approach Through 5e Learning Cycle Model on Students' Understanding of Chemical Reactions and Energy Concepts, and Their Motivation to Learn Chemistry. Retrieved June 25, 2024 from <https://Etd.Lib.Metu.Edu.Tr/Upload/12614466/Index.pdf>
- Creswell, J. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach*. 4th edition. SAGE Publications, Inc. <http://doi.org/10.1002/nha3.20258>
- *Dioneda Jr., Isagani P., Localization and Contextualization in Teaching Biology for Grade 7 Students of Paliparan National High School for School Year 2018–2019 (2019). *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, Volume 1, Issue 3, September 2019, E-ISSN 2651-771X, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3461307>.
- *Dumanjog, N. E. (2020). Effectiveness of Contextualized Learning Activities in Teaching Force. In *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* (Vol. 9, Issue 11). <https://www.ijsr.net>
- Etorbro, B., & Fabinu, E. (2017). Students' perceptions of difficult concepts in biology in senior secondary schools in Lagos State. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 16, 139-147. <https://doi.org/10.4314/gjedr.v16i2.8>
- Fortus, D., Krajcik, J., Dershimer, R. C., Marx, R. W., & Mamlok-Naaman, R. (2005). Design-based science and real-world problem-solving. *International Journal of Science Education*, 27(7), 855-879. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500690500038165>
- Gebre, E., Saroyan, A., & Bracewell, R. (2014). Students' engagement in technology rich classrooms and its relationship to professors' conceptions of effective teaching. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 45(1), 83-96.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12001>
- Gilbert, J. K. (2006). Context based chemistry education on the nature of "context" in chemical education. *International Journal of Science Education*, 28 (9), 957-976.
- Gough, D., Oliver, S., & Thomas, J. (2017). *An introduction to systematic reviews* (2nd ed.). London, England: Sage.
- GutWill-Wise, J., P., (2001). The Impact of active and context based learning in introductory chemistry courses: an early evaluation of the modular approach. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 78 (5), 684–690
- Haidich A. B. (2010). Meta-analysis in medical research. *Hippokratia*, 14(Suppl 1), 29–37.
- Harbord R.M., Harris, R.J., & Sterne, J.A. (2009). Updated tests for small-study effects in meta-analyses. *The Stata Journal*, 9 (2), 197-210.
- Harzing, A.W. (2007). Publish or perish software. Available from <https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish>.
- Hasruddin, & Putri, S. E. (2014). Analysis of Students' Learning Difficulties in Fungi Subject Matter Grade X Science of Senior High School Medan Academic Year 2013 / 2014. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(8), 269–276.
- Ibrahim (2007). *Penelitian dan Penilaian Pendidikan*. Bandung : Sinar Baru Algensindo

- İlhan, N., Yıldırım, A. & Sadi-Yılmaz, S. (2016). The effect of context-based chemical equilibrium on grade 11 students' learning, motivation and constructivist learning environment. *International Journal of Environment & Science Education*, 11(9), 3117-3137.
- *Jusriana, J. A., Suarti, S., Rasyid, R., & Mariani, S. (2022). The Effect of the Contextual Teaching and Learning (CTL) Learning Model Based on Simulation Media on the Motivation and Learning Outcomes of Students in Physics Learning. *Journal of Teaching and Learning Physics*, 7(2), 88–96.
<https://doi.org/10.15575/jotalp.v7i2.17116>
- *Kazeni, M., & Onwu, G. (2013). Comparative Effectiveness of Context-based and Traditional Approaches in Teaching Genetics: Student Views and Achievement. *African Journal of Research in Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 17(1–2), 50–62.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10288457.2013.826970>
- Lemke, J. L. (2001). Articulating communities: Sociocultural perspectives on science education. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 38(3), 296-316.
[https://doi.org/10.1002/1098-2736\(200103\)38:3<296::AID-TEA1007>3.0.CO;2-R](https://doi.org/10.1002/1098-2736(200103)38:3<296::AID-TEA1007>3.0.CO;2-R)
- Lin, L., & Aloe, A. M. (2021). Evaluation of various estimators for standardized mean difference in meta-analysis. *Statistics in medicine*, 40(2), 403–426.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.8781>
- Liquin, E.G. & Gopnik, A. (2022). Children are more exploratory and learn more than adults in an approach-avoid task. *Cognition*, 218, 2022, 104940, ISSN 0010-0277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2021.104940>
- *Lubis, E.L.S.W. & Rahmania, S. (2022). The Effectiveness of Contextual Teaching and Learning with Multimedia to Increase Student's Achievement on Hydrocarbon Topic. *Current Research in Chemistry Education* 1 (1).
- Magwilang, E. B. "Teaching Chemistry In Context: Its Effects On Students' Motivation, Attitudes and Achievement in Chemistry," *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 15 (4). 2016.
- *Magwilang, E.B. (2016). Teaching Chemistry in Context: Its Effects on Students' Motivation, Attitudes and Achievement in Chemistry. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 15 (4).
- Magwilang, E. B. (2016). Teaching Chemistry in Context: Its Effects on Students' Motivation, Attitudes & Achievement in Chemistry. *International Journal of Teaching, Learning & Educational Research*, 15(4).
- Magwilang, E. B. (2016). Teaching Chemistry in Context: Its Effects on Students' Motivation, Attitudes & Achievement in Chemistry. *International Journal of Teaching, Learning & Educational Research*, 15(4).
- Nagarajan, S., & Overton, T. (2019). Promoting systems thinking using project-and problem-based learning. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 96(12), 2901- 2909.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.9b00358>
- Nair A. S. (2019). Publication bias - Importance of studies with negative results!. *Indian journal of anaesthesia*, 63(6), 505–507. https://doi.org/10.4103/ija.IJA_142_19
- Özay Köse E. and Çam Tosun F., (2013). Context Based Learning' Effects on Achievement and Scientific Process Skills in Biology Teaching. *Iğdır Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Dergisi / Iğdır Univ. J. Inst. Sci. & Tech.* 3(4), 33-41.

- *Ozkan, G. & Selcuk, G. S. (2015). The Effectiveness of Conceptual Change Texts and Context-Based Learning on Students' Conceptual Achievement. (2015). In *Journal of Baltic Science Education* (Vols. 14–14, Issue 6, pp. 753–754). <http://www.scientiasocialis.lt/jbse>
- Patterson, E. A., Campbell, P. B., Busch-Vishniac, I., & Guillaume, D. W. (2011). The effect of context on student engagement in engineering. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 36(3), 211-224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2011.575218>
- Pigott, T. D., & Polanin, J. R. (2020). Methodological Guidance Paper: High-Quality Meta-Analysis in a Systematic Review. *Review of Educational Research*, 90(1), 24-46. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654319877153>
- Pilot, A. & Bulte, A. (2006). Why do you need to know context based education? *International Journal of Science Education*, 28 (9), 953- 956.
- Ramsden, J. M., (1997). How does a context-based approach influence understanding of key chemical ideas at 16+?. *International Journal of Science Education*, 19 (6), 697–710
- Sadi Yilmaz, S. (2013). The Effects of the context- based learning approach on the training of chemical changes unit [Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation]. Ataturk University.
- Sadi Yilmaz, S., Yıldırım, A., & İlhan, N. (2022). Effects of the Context-Based Learning Approach on the Teaching of Chemical Changes Unit. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 2022, 19(1), 218-236. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2022.119>
- Schwartz, A. T., (2006). Context-based chemistry education contextualised chemistry education: The American experience. *International Journal of Science Education*, 28 (9), 977–998.
- Sevian, H., Dori, Y. J., & Parchmann, I. (2018). How does STEM context-based learning work: What we know and what we still do not know. *International Journal of Science Education*, 40(10), 1095-1107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500693.2018.1470346>
- Sterne, J.A.C. Sutton, A., ... Higgins, J.P.T. (2011). Recommendations for examining and interpreting funnel plot asymmetry in meta-analyses of randomised controlled trials. *BMJ* 2011;342:d4002. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.d4002>
- Suryawati, E., & Osman, K. (2017). Contextual learning: Innovative approach towards the development of students' scientific attitude and natural science performance. *Eurasia Journal of mathematics, science and technology education*, 14(1), 61-76.
- *Taratara-Fadero, A.M. (2022). Effect of Contextual Inquiry Approach on Interest Towards Science and Achievement in Earth Science among Grade 10 Students. *Romblon State University Research Journal*, 4 (1), 34-39.
- Valdmann, A., Rannikmae, M., & Holbrook, J. (2016). Determining the effectiveness of a CPD program for enhancing science teachers' self-efficacy towards motivational context-based teaching. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 15(3), 284. <https://doi.org/10.33225/jbse/16.15.281>
- van Dulmen, T. H. H., Visser, T. C., Pepin, B., & McKenney, S. (2022). Teacher and student engagement when using learning materials based on the context of cutting-edge chemistry research. *Research in Science & Technological*

- Education. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02635143.2022.2070147>
- Vogelzang, J., Admiraal, W. F., & van Driel, J. H. (2019). Scrum methodology as an effective scaffold to promote students' learning and motivation in context-based secondary chemistry education. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 15(12), em1783. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/109941>
- Wai, H.O. & Khine, S.S. (2020). An Investigation into the Difficulties of Students in Learning Biology. *J. Myanmar Acad. Arts Sci.* 2020, 8 (9c).
- Walker, C. L., & Shore, B. M. (2015). Understanding Classroom Roles in Inquiry Education: Linking Role Theory and Social Constructivism to the Concept of Role Diversification. *Sage Open*, 5(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244015607584>
- Westwood, P. (1996). Effective teaching. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 21 (1), 66-74.
- Yilmaz, S.S., Yildirim, A. & Ilhan, N. (2022). Effects of the Context-Based Learning Approach on the Teaching of Chemical Changes Unit. *Journal of Turkish Science Education*, 2022, 19(1), 218-236. <https://doi.org/10.36681/tused.2022.119>
- Yu, K. C., Fan, S. C., & Lin, K. Y. (2015). Enhancing students' problem-solving skills through context based learning. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 13, 1377-1401. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-014-9567-4>
- Zwetsloot, P. P., Van Der Naald, M., Sena, E. S., Howells, D. W., IntHout, J., De Groot, J. A., Chamuleau, S. A., MacLeod, M. R., & Wever, K. E. (2017). Standardized mean differences cause funnel plot distortion in publication bias assessments. *eLife*, 6, e24260. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.24260>